

Postcolonial Perspective in The Tempest: Shakespeare's Relevance in Today's Very Different World

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ABSTRACT

The twentieth century brought about a new form of understanding, producing and living art that has become a mean to react against the oppression that different groups suffered for centuries. Post-colonial criticism is an approach of analysis that questions racial identity and gender equity. This study investigates how Shakespeare's plays relate to the social codes and the more recent history of the reception of Shakespearean drama within decolonisation movements. The Tempest by Shakespeare is defined as a postcolonial text because the colonised is represented in regarding cultural hybridity in which the Self and the Other enlance the colonial experience. Literature has naturally given a voice to these omitted groups and this play is thought to be an early post-colonial work by some scholars. Shakespeare had intended to criticise the European attack of the new lands to the West, and the theme of colonialism is outrightly presented in The Tempest. Post-colonial reading of the text examines the projection of the colonial experience back to Europe. Slavery, colonialism, and the power of changing other civilisations by the West are themes to make inferences.

INTRODUCTION

The characterisation makes Shakespearean tragedies unique. Shakespeare's plays has continued to be performed because despite characters are kings, queens, and princesses, they seem quite brilliant and alive to viewers. They hold multidimensional human characterisations on the stage where people can associate with them thoroughly. Shakespeare (1564-1616) is a master of the plot, and many of his plays are still relevant to the present. Although most of his plays do not contain historical facts, they look incredibly entertaining and still are performed all over the world. We still study Shakespeare because he was intelligent at play-writing, and his vivid imagery and important themes never failed. All of his plays have patterns, and they include hidden themes and complicated conclusion. In Shakespeare's time, a new play was acted out every few weeks, so writers did not have much time to write complicated plays, but Shakespearean comedies included deeply tragic and very human moments. Moreover, while the mixture of genres is acceptable today, it was not regular in the days of Shakespeare, because it was a radical change in the way plays were presented.

1. Shakespeare as the Master of English

The relevance of William Shakespeare in reflections upon the past and current issues is featured among researchers who focus on literature. From a purely linguistic viewpoint, Shakespeare introduced thousands of words and phrases to the English language, along with new concepts and grammatical structures by changing the normal word order. Although Shakespeare's language sometimes seems old to modern eyes, it was quite courageous and forward thinking for his time. Shakespeare created words to describe words that formerly were impossible to identify situations and events, but later, they elevated the English language greatly. Shakespeare's explorations of poetic form and grammar also expanded the opportunity for other authors who worked after him. By exceeding traditional borders, Shakespearean tragedies present the traditional tragedies with a great deal of comic mood.

The stories of Shakespeare are timeless, and many of the themes come up in modern literature, films, and theatre. From behaviours which have been shaped to the words and sentence structure, Shakespearean plays have elements of modern society. For instance, Hamlet is an indecisive overthinker, Romeo is a persistent romancer than a lover faithful unto death,

and Lady Macbeth is an ambitious female politician who gains her end. There are the reasons why Shakespeare's works are still relevant in today's very different world. His plays contain timeless themes such as love, friendship, and revenge. Everyone heard about his tragedies and comedies that have been adapted countless times for stage, film, musicals, and opera. Shakespearean characters are mortal and real. The characters in Shakespeare are like us, even though they may be kings, queens, noblemen, and women. They are weak in many ways, like Macbeth, who becomes miserable because of ambition, or Hamlet, who struggles with the death of his father.

It is not surprising that Shakespeare is one of the most quoted authors in the Oxford Dictionary. His plays are full of quotable quotes, and he is a source of commonly used phrases and words today. Some of his phrases are so well known that we have forgotten the man who first said it, such as "a rose by any other word," (Shakespeare, 2003, 107) or "parting is such sweet sorrow" (Shakespeare, 2003, 114) that are references to *Romeo and Juliet*. Shakespeare was quite a forward-thinking author in an age when women were not even allowed to perform on stage. His female characters—then played by men—were not shelved; in fact, many of them had critical roles to play in his dramas. Viola, in the *Twelfth Night*, Lady Macbeth, Katherine of *Henry VIII* or the Portia of *The Merchant of Venice* had a significant influence on English literature.

2. Dramatic Post-Colonial Aura

Many critics believe that as an artistic expression, the drama is the oldest literary genre dating back to when humanity started to present stories. Dramatic language is a paradox. When it is brief, concrete, and oral, it reveals the beauty of a literary work. Besides, it is extensive and explanatory, because unlike other genres, it has been written to be heard and understood with no chance of re-reading it. It is a short-lived art, as it lasts the length of a performance, but it has been produced to continue the test of time. It is written to be spoken. If drama is considered as a language, postcolonial drama's language is worthy to be discussed. Postcolonial drama presents difficulties that make it unique. This type of drama developed within nations that were formerly colonised by Western imperial powers with a strong need to recover local histories and local traditions.

From postcolonialism perspective in which literature counts with a new voice for traditionally omitted groups, drama symbolises the recovery of cultural heritage in the best form. The appropriation of symbolic spaces on stage is always metaphoric to gain

representation in society. Postcolonial literature that is a stylized clarification of life, changed dramatically during the twentieth century. Years of academic training and cultural conditioning in postcolonial discourse have settled us with mental plans to understand heterosexuality, masculinity, whiteness, and Western discourse easily. Today, attention has moved to give particular importance to dialectal, ideological, and verbal problems, and consider the areas of characterisation in the context of literature where cultural similarities may be nonexistent in the target language. Postcolonial literature is a mixed term that refers to different cultures that originate it. The common goal of postcolonial literature is the search to improve local histories and traditions. Moreover, the postcolonial drama tends to break the barriers with the intention of becoming comprehensive to the audience in their quest for identity.

3. Colonial Mentality in *The Tempest*

The Tempest by Shakespeare tells the story of a strange island settled by the magician Prospero and his daughter, Miranda, who live in a cave on the island that is also inhabited by the ugly half-human creature, Caliban. The educated noble, Prospero, comes to the island and the native, Caliban, helps Prospero by introducing him to the island. Prospero reduces Caliban to a savage slave and servant; thus, consequently, Prospero becomes a self-proclaimed ruler of the island and Caliban as the wretched slave. At the end of the play, Prospero returns to Europe to decolonise his island and liberate his slaves by giving up the magical powers that enabled him to control Caliban on the island.

The Tempest is a play written from a cultural point of view and examined with many different literary theories. One of them is a postcolonial reading of the play, especially when the focus is on the character of Caliban. The need for communicating for human beings is a core element for social development. Thus, language is the first thing to be passed on from coloniser to the colonised. In *The Tempest*, Caliban is taught English by Prospero and Miranda and he begins to speak it so fluently. Caliban, however, recognised the importance of education, citing Prospero's books as the source of all of his magical power. When others fail to see the significance of the books and are more interested in the beautiful clothes they find, Caliban mocks them.

Prospero's resistance to language proves the natives' attitude toward European colonisation. The court jester, Trinculo's aim to take Caliban to England is an apparent reference to Europeans who took Indian people to America and exhibit them in a sort of zoo is

another sample of post-colonialism. G. A. Wikes says “*The Tempest* can readily be seen as a text which is complicit with colonial power. Prospero is the usurping invader, nervous about the legitimacy of his rule, his language lessons seen as an attempt to eradicate his own culture, or to bring it under imperialist control.” (Wikes, 1995, 42) Caliban acknowledges that Prospero has taught him his language but curses and threatens him when he reacts to Miranda and Prospero: “You taught me language and my profit on’t / Is I know how to curse. The red plague rid you / For learning me your language!” (Shakespeare, 2009, 19)

Studying *The Tempest*, and Caliban and Prospero characters, in particular, present a relationship that at first seems to be equally beneficial. Caliban welcomed Prospero and Miranda to his island. Prospero tells Miranda that they cannot do without Caliban because he provides their firewood. Prospero finds Caliban useful and almost vital because the need for materials is within the colonised society, and Caliban does not complain of being oppressed. He complains of being deceived. Caliban feels that his first wild enslavement does not seem to cause the gap between him and Prospero; somewhat, Prospero’s treatments in the time are disrupting. *The Tempest* shows us how the relationship between coloniser and colonised may seem to be equally beneficial, but also details the origin of this relationship into hatred and disloyalty. It is also studied as the psychology of the colonised.

Caliban is a two-hander character. He is a stereotype character who repeats cultural ideas about black sexuality and has desires of colonising. Concurrently, Caliban seems a round character when considering the relationship between Caliban and Prospero is comprising engrossing sexuality between the coloniser and the colonised. Caliban is accused of raping Miranda, and this is a claim that Caliban never denies. Instead, he comments that Prospero upsets the applecart. We may look at this incident in many ways: In one hand, Caliban’s (racial) weakness and his position to desire Miranda ruin him. It is on the other hand, a metaphor for black male sexuality to be naturally uncontrollable and violent. “Shakespeare, with the art of male and female characterizations, has skillfully created the colonizing process which bears the testimony of today’s post-colonialism as well” (Iseni, 2014, 16). Prospero finds Caliban as a potential rapist of his daughter Miranda (Shakespeare, 2009, 17), but Miranda justifies their enslavement of Caliban. She says they tried to civilise him. Prospero’s address to Caliban or the coloniser’s attitude in civilising the natives is represented as:

Abhorred slave,
Which any print of goodness wilt
not take,
Being capable of all ill! I pitied
thee,
Took pains to make thee speak,
taught thee each hour
One thing or other. When thou
didst not—savage!—
Know thine own meaning, but
wouldst gabble like
A thing most brutish, I endowed
thy purposes
With words that made them
known. (Shakespeare, 2009, 19)

In *Black Skin, White Masks* Frantz Fanon described the racial hatred to the white father who is uncomfortable with his daughter’s black lover. (Fanon, 48) Caliban’s foolish attempt to gain Miranda sexually could be seen as his internalisation of the white man’s (Prospero’s) power over him and Caliban’s manner to gain a desire in Prospero’s society. However, as an uncivilised savage, Caliban tries to succeed so through violence. Michel Foucault states power is productive, and it comes from knowledge. He says, “What makes power hold good, what makes it accepted, is simply the fact that it doesn’t only weigh on us as a force that says no, but that it traverses and produces things, it induces pleasure, forms knowledge, produces discourse” (Foucault, 1980, 119) They often imagine that power is nothing but the ability of powerful agents in exercising their will on the powerless people and forcing them to do what they do not want. Foucault criticises this attitude by saying that power is more like a strategy and a form of doing things than grasping. Thus, knowledge is an instrument of power and the colonizers use language to express their dominance to the colonized. Caliban acknowledges the power of magic of Prospero: “I must obey, his Art is of such power/ It would control my dam’s god Setebos / And make a vassal of him” (Shakespeare, 2009, 20).

4. Post-colonial Reading of *The Tempest*

Colonialism, exploration of new geographical spaces and control of those lands by the explorers and opening up of new frontiers and new land which was a big issue during Shakespeare’s time began much earlier with the discovery of America. Prospero’s confiscate of Sycorax’s land, subduing her, and his treatment of the natives of the island and imposing his own culture on the people of the land in *The Tempest* is interpreted as the drama of colonisation. Like the Europeans who usurped the land of native Americans

and enslaved them, Prospero is seen as a ruler who is usurping Caliban's Island and putting him under slavery and undermining him as a monster. As George Lamming states, "modern Caliban is a greedy learner. He can learn methods of investigation as thoroughly as any Prospero with similar facilities" (Lamming, 1995, 159). He says exile and paradox are only one layer to the story. Although Prospero tries to teach the language to Caliban, he remains at the end what he was at the beginning. Dudalski says;

The contemporary Caliban is aware of his relation to Prospero, and he uses Prospero's tools to write himself, to write his history without having to ask permission to his former master. Even having inherited a legacy of dispossession, the contemporary Caliban, or as Lamming uses sometimes, the descendants of Caliban, now belong to an age of negotiation of the relationship between past and present. (Dudalski, 2013, 48)

Caliban, here, represents all the natives who do not want to be prisoners of colonialism. Bhat says, "Caliban scolds himself for trusting Prospero and letting him know all the secrets of the land. By using the knowledge that he gained in the company of Caliban, Prospero enslaves Caliban and after making him a slave, he ill-treats him. Thus the play by depicting the exploitation of the colonized by the colonizer, attempts to highlight and condemn the existing ideologies of colonization." (Bhat, 2017, 32) Caliban dwells on belongingness by telling; "This Island is mine, by Sycorax, my mother." (Shakespeare, 2009, 18) Caliban's statement, "they all do hate him as rootedly as I" implies that natives hate Prospero and want freedom from his colonisation although they do not have the courage to revolt against him. When Stephano says "This will prove a brave kingdom to me, where / I shall have my music for nothing," Caliban answers "When Prospero is destroyed." (Shakespeare, 2009, 51) Singh says,

Miranda and Prospero's justifications of their enslavement of the 'savage' Caliban, whose 'vile race' (1.2.358) lacks natural goodness, are strongly challenged by post-colonial criticism. Unlike generations of earlier readers, post-colonial critics view Prospero's and Miranda's

relations with Caliban as an allegory of European colonialism – one that reveals Shakespeare's ambivalence toward Prospero's power. Europeans' colonising activities among non-European natives they encountered in the Americas, Africa, and the Caribbean were based on the premise of the 'civilising mission'. This mission assumed that the natives lacked any culture or formal language until the Europeans brought them the 'gifts' of Western language and culture. If the natives resisted European paternal rule, then they were labelled as 'savages', beyond redemption. (Singh, 2016, 1)

Alden T. Vaughan remarks: "If Shakespeare, however obliquely, meant Caliban to personify America's natives, his intention miscarried almost completely." (Vaughan, 1999, 138) Shakespeare "by no means supporting the civilized, white race of Prospero as being supreme which is the ground for most of the post-colonial critics to consider the play as a text favoring colonialism. As discussed earlier this is further strengthened by the epilogue where Prospero himself feels he is under somebody else's power" (Chand, 2013, 39). The play's readers find Caliban as a mythic, archetype monstrous and sinful creature, but not as colonised Native American. Meredith Anne Skura explains:

Evidence for the play's original reception is of course extraordinarily difficult to find, but in the two nearly contemporaneous responses to Caliban that we do know about, the evidence for a colonialist response is at best ambiguous. In *Bartholomew Fair* (1614) Jonson refers scornfully to a "servant-monster," and the Folio identifies Caliban as a "salvage and deformed slave" in the cast list. Both "monster" and "salvage" are firmly rooted in the discourse of Old World wild men...In other words, these two seventeenth-century responses tend to invoke the universal and not the particular implications of

Caliban's condition. (Skura, 1989, 64)

Shakespeare was familiar to the dynamics of the privileged and the oppressed in the New World and British colonisation. Despite he was not living in a postcolonial time and the adverse effects of colonialism are only coming to light recently. Shakespeare was discussing outcomes of humans abusing power while he did not know much about postcolonial discourse. Meredith Anne Skura discusses, "in trying to understand the New World representatives of 'uncivilised' human nature, Prospero, like other Europeans, had imposed Old (and New) World stereotypes of innocence and monstrosity on the Native Americans, distorting perception with hope and fear" (Skura, 1989, 44). Discussing Caliban's resemblance to "the demonised women, Moors, and Jews," (Ibid.) Skura goes over Mannoni's idea that Prospero displayed the psychology of colonials who projected their disowned traits onto New World natives.

CONCLUSION

The popularity of Shakespeare is a witness to his relevance. Shakespeare helped not only to the English language but to the manner in which people think and behave. *The Tempest* is an original book in the field of post-colonial theory. This play is thought to be an early post-colonial work by some scholars. Shakespeare shaped society in many ways that made him dressed up the characters of Prospero and Caliban are regularly reread in the colonial contexts, restate the colonial perspective and also the perspective of the colonised. Postcolonial plays provide the frequent trouble of the old colonies through portrayals of ritual and carnival, body politics such as race and gender, and also different types of Neo-Imperialisms. Many post-colonial theorists and literary critics focus on Caliban who has been tied to the West's image of the native: strange in appearance, objectified, and dehumanised. *The Tempest* as an allegory of Colonialism and one of the earliest postcolonial works in English literature depicts the power hierarchy in the colonised territory by showing the struggle of the oppressed native Caliban and conveying the white man's dependence on his native slaves.

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